

CAUSALITY AND CHAOS: ON ARISTOTELIAN METAPHYSICS IN ANCIENT EGYPTIAN COSMOGONIES*

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to demonstrate that the ancient Egyptians had a profound understanding of abstract, philosophical concepts rather than a mere collection of primitive beliefs, founded in mytho–religion. In order to achieve this, we compare some ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies and Aristotle’s (fundamental) metaphysical concepts of causality, actuality and potentiality. We are very cautious not to force a Western framework upon an ancient culture, nor do we attempt the paradoxical quest to find an origin of Aristotelian metaphysics in ancient Egypt. On the contrary, by comparing fundamental, religious texts from ancient Egypt with fundamental, philosophical works of ancient Hellas, we attempt to highlight similar, abstract thought processes in both cultures. Part one explains the ancient Hellenic separation of mytho–religion and rational Philosophy, and the reasons why this cut did not occur in ancient Egypt. We find the latter in the crucial obligation of maintaining Ma’at in daily –continuous and nearly identical ways– to which the ancient Egyptians had to adapt their Sciences and Philosophies, instead of separating religion and reason. Part two, then, compares in detail the above mentioned famous Aristotelian concepts with the Heliopolitan, Hermopolitan and Memphite Cosmogonies. This comparison touches –among others– upon the important religious–philosophical concepts of Creation, the origin of Death and introduction of Evil in the ordered world. It furthermore explains why the rather obscure concept of Aristotelian *Prima Materia*, which causes an unexpressed, but obvious «Duality» between Aristotle’s Prime Mover and Prime Matter (eternal *Actuality* and *Potentiality*) does not create any problems in the metaphysical nature of (the primeval god of the watery Abyss) Nūn. Based on the latter, we conclude (by introducing our current research) on how the old Egyptological problem (of whether Evil in ancient Egypt was perceived as being contingent or present since Creation) appears to have been metaphysically circumvented altogether by the ancient Egyptians themselves.

I. INTRODUCTION

I.1. ANCIENT HELLENIC VERSUS ANCIENT EGYPTIAN PHILOSOPHY: The Philosophy in ancient Egypt has long been neglected, devaluated or simply ignored. Despite the ground–breaking works in this direction by several Egyptologists¹ modern, scholastic definitions of ancient Philosophy are unlikely to include the old wisdom of the ancient Egyptians. Rather, the western conception of ancient Philosophy centres almost exclusively on the works of the ancient Hellenes². The reason for this is the seemingly sharp contrast between the rational thoughts of the Hellenic *Φιλοσοφία* (= *love of wisdom*) and the mytho–theological concepts of the ancient Egyptians based on the divinization of elements and interrelations of gods, which is often considered the naïve way of an ancient people to understand and familiarize with the world

* I should like to thank Dr Dr Amanda–Alice MARAVELIA, as well as two anonymous referees (a Philosopher and an Egyptologist) for their very useful comments, corrections and additions.

¹ See e.g.: HORNUNG, 2005; ALLEN, 1988; ALLEN *et al.*, 1989; VERHOEVEN & GRAEFE, 1991; ASSMANN, 2001.

² See SEDLEY, 1998: 33–36.

around them³. What Scholars of ancient Philosophy tend to ignore is the fact that the philosophical concepts of both civilizations originated from a similar point of reference⁴. Before the ancient Hellēnes experienced their famous transition from myth to reason, they maintained similar creation accounts as the ancient Egyptians⁵. In early Hellenic Mythology there also exists a time of *Chaos*, before the development of the *Kosmos* (literally the ordered whole), and the elements in it. Homer even speaks of a great primeval ocean (*Ωκεανός*), the *begetter of the gods*⁶. The first element said to have developed from this chaos was Earth, who produced Sky followed by other primeval elements, such as Night, Day and Aether. Earth and Sky, on their part produced the genealogies of gods. Other Cosmogonies, such as the *Orphic* and related myths describe how the elements developed from a primordial egg, or from the void created when Earth and Sky —two originally fused beings— were separated⁷. When being confronted with these themes, one cannot help but be reminded of the ancient Egyptian concepts of the primeval water Nūn, the primordial mound or egg which carried or hatched the creator god, the separation of Geb (Earth) and Nūt (Sky) by their father Shū (Air) in order to create a space that would make evolution in a physical world possible, and the generations of gods derived from the union of Nūt and Geb⁸. Indeed, the fundamental differences between ancient Hellenic and ancient Egyptian *Cosmogonies* and *Cosmologies* cannot be found in their content but merely in their socio-popular perception⁹.

Ancient Hellenic Cosmogonies were perceived as mythological stories, composed by pre-Socratic philosophers and theologians, in order to explain abstract natural and physio-psychological phenomena, as well as to find an answer to the universal questions about the origin, nature and purpose of life¹⁰. Mythological texts were compiled as large volumes of narrative stories revolving around the origin of the world, gods, demons and humans, such as the life, affairs and interrelations of gods and their connection with the human sphere¹¹. These narratives were primarily oral/poetic, but survive in art drawings, and predominantly in the heroic/historical literature of ancient Hellas. The *corpus* of Hellenic Mythology is too broad to be treated in details here, but it can be summarized under three major headlines: **1.** Myths concerning the origin of the world, elements, gods and living beings. **2.** Myths concerning the time when deities, supernatural beings and humans mingled on Earth. and **3.** Narrative heroic myths, such as the *Odyssey* in which divine interactions were less frequent, but were still applied to explain luck, misfortune and ironic twists of fate¹².

Especially myths falling under the second or third category allowed for the eventual mental emancipation between mytho-divine and rational scientific concepts¹³. In ancient Hellas natural and fateful events were thought to be caused either by a furious or alternatively satisfied deity. Gods could enter the human realm unnoticed to steer chaos or misfortune among the mortal, and even cause wars, as probably most prominently exemplified in the narrative of

³ See LLOYD, 1975: 198 ff; TOBIN, 1988: 169-83.

⁴ See LLOYD, 1975: 198-205; SEDLEY, 1998: 34 ff.

⁵ See ASSMANN, 2005: 13 ff, 23 ff; LLOYD, 1975: 198-200.

⁶ See LLOYD, 1975: 200 ff; BURKET, 1987: esp. 1-9, 190 ff.

⁷ See LLOYD, 1975: 200 ff; BURKET, 1987: 275 ff; MARAVELIA, 2006: 365-69 & fig. IV.14; 401 ff & fig. V.4.

⁸ See BONNET, 2000, 864-867: art. «Weltbeginn». Cf. also MARAVELIA, 2003: 55-72.

⁹ See ASSMANN, 2005: 13 ff; TOBIN, 1988: 170 ff. HORNUNG, 1987: 113 ff. [EDITOR'S NOTE: Better to use the term *Cosmology* instead of *Cosmogony*, which refers to modern scientific notions; however we do keep the author's term].

¹⁰ See LLOYD, 1975: 200-202; BURKET, 1987: 190 ff.

¹¹ See LLOYD, 1975: 200-202; BURKET, 1987: 216 ff.

¹² See BURKET, 1987: 1-9, 215 ff.

¹³ See ASSMANN, 2005: 13 ff, 23 ff; LLOYD, 1975: 200-202; BURKET, 1987: 190 ff; TOBIN, 1988: 171 ff.

the Trojan War¹⁴. Apart from these interferences the creation of the world had brought about two separate spheres for divine and mortal beings, and generally both gods and humans minded their own businesses and affairs in their own realms¹⁵. For the ancient Hellēnes however the fear of misfortune caused by an enraged god remained always present. This fear began to vanish when increased scientific understanding discovered more rational explanations for previously unexplainable environmental and astronomical phenomena, such as thunderstorms, solar and lunar eclipses, or the motion of celestial bodies¹⁶. Step by step early Hellenic philosophers eliminated the supernatural and improvable myths in favour of scientific facts and rational explanations, and thus paved the way for modern western Philosophy and Science¹⁷.

FIGURE I: The symbolic killing of ‘Apophis (*ꜥꜣꜣ*) and evil in the Netherworld by the creator–god Atūm. Detail of a painting from the Tomb of Pharaoh Ramesses I (KV 16), at the Valley of the Kings (c. 1300 BC).

In ancient Egypt the situation was fundamentally different. Here too myth–theological ideas were employed to explain obscure natural and abstract phenomena, the origin and purpose of the ordered world, its beings and the beyond, and in order to familiarize the dangerous and unknown¹⁸. Unlike in ancient Hellas these ideas were not compiled as coherent mythological narratives, but survive in countless literary, pictorial and monumental sources. They were usually created around a local deity (or group of deities) by their respective priests, and often served propagandistic purposes¹⁹. More so than in ancient Hellas environmental and political changes affected the composition of myths and religious ideas, so that ideas and concepts not only varied with place but also with time. It is thus not surprising that the content of Egyptian religious and mythological concepts of more than 3000 years often differs substantially²⁰. These diverse interpretations of the natural and supernatural were perceived as complementary and adjacent, rather than contradicting concepts²¹. The reasons for that lie in the very nature of ancient Egyptian religion. Unlike its ancient Hellenic counterparts, ancient

¹⁴ See LLOYD, 1975: 201 ff; BURKET, 1987: 276 ff.

¹⁵ See BURKET, 1987: 119 ff.

¹⁶ See LLOYD, 1975: 209 ff. Cf. also MARAVELIA, 2006: 3-4.

¹⁷ See LLOYD, 1975: 207 ff; BURKET, 1987: 305 ff; SEDLEY, 1998: 33-36.

¹⁸ See HORNUNG, 2005: 62 ff; TOBIN, 1988: 170 ff; PINCH, 2003: 1 ff.

¹⁹ See PINCH, 2003: 8 ff; TOBIN, 1988: 172 ff.

²⁰ See PINCH, 2003: 1-56; ASSMANN, 2003: 15 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 36 ff.

²¹ See DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 42 ff.; ALLEN, 1988: 12 ff; COHN, 1993: 5 ff.

Egyptian mythology was not merely a way of explaining the world. It was an essential part of it²². From the very moment of creation the Cosmos was maintained by *Ma'at*. *Ma'at* is generally translated as the Cosmic and Social Order of the world, but also as justice, righteousness and good conduct, concepts that contribute directly to its perpetuation. It was this Cosmic Order that prevented the physical world in which divine and mortal life could develop from resolving back into the primeval chaos from which it originated²³. Unlike in Hellenic Mythology this chaos was not defeated at the beginning of time but was constantly present at the fringes of the ordered world²⁴. It was, thus, the duty of both gods and humans to obtain *Ma'at*. This was essentially secured by the undisturbed, daily course of the Sun, which symbolized the original act of creation every day anew. In the human realm *Ma'at* was maintained too by means of piety, social justice and righteous deeds, which were monitored and secured by the divine representative on Earth, the Pharaoh²⁵. This universal interest of preserving *Ma'at* tightly interconnected gods and humans, and consequently almost inseparably bound the ancient Egyptians to their mytho–theological ideas. Not the fear of personal misfortune, but of complete annihilation of the world was the prime motivator²⁶. Associated therewith was the lack of actual Natural Sciences that helped emancipate the ancient Hellēnes²⁷. In ancient Egypt Science was part of religion and served the exclusive purpose of preventing or reversing disruptions of *Ma'at* by means of rituals and magic²⁸. Applied Science, such as astronomical observations, or the preparation of medicines was considered nothing more than an empirical tool in this process²⁹. Furthermore, mythology and history were not as strictly separated as in ancient Hellas. The event of creation in ancient Egypt and the subsequent rule of the gods on Earth were perceived as a timely distant, but not eternally far, actual event³⁰. This too contributed to the tight interlinking between the ancient Egyptians and their religious beliefs, and consequently hindered a similar development from myth to reason as had occurred in ancient Hellas³¹. It seems therefore easy to conclude that ancient Egyptians never left this religious, mytho–symbolic sphere in favour of rational philosophical evaluation of abstract concepts.

That this is in fact a rather superfluous perception of the ancient Egyptian body of thought has been criticized by several Scholars³². The current author believes that only such a comparison can help eliminate some of the prejudices concerning the «naïve» mytho–theological beliefs of the ancient Egyptians in contrast to the highly abstract, rational Philosophy of the ancient Hellēnes, and show that the ancient Egyptians, too, were able to think abstractly rather than only symbolically, as has been predicated by some³³. In order to achieve this, we decided to compare the mythological basis of ancient Egyptian religion —the Cosmogonies— with what is commonly considered the roots of modern, western Philosophy: Aristotle's *Metaphysics*. In order to compare both concepts properly, it is necessary to briefly survey them.

²² See HORNUNG, 2005: 62 ff; ASSMANN, 2001: 1-16; DUNAND & ZIVIE–COCHE, 2001: 6 ff; cf. MARAVELIA, 2007: 1243-50.

²³ See ASSMANN, 1995B: esp. 160-199; TOBIN, 1988: 170 ff; COHN, 1993: 10-16.

²⁴ See LLOYD, 1975: 198 ff; COHN, 1993: 3 ff; HORNUNG, 1956: 28-32.

²⁵ See esp. ASSMANN, 1995B; COHN, 1993: 11 ff.

²⁶ See TOBIN, 1988: 170 ff; ASSMANN, 2005: esp. 17 ff, 22 ff; ASSMANN, 1994: 93-100.

²⁷ See LLOYD, 1975: 202 ff, 207 ff.

²⁸ See PINCH, 2006; DUNAND & ZIVIE–COCHE, 2004: esp. 122 ff.

²⁹ See n. 28, *supra*.

³⁰ See KÁKOSY, 1963: 18, where L. Kákosy gives an estimated, historical time–frame of this event as perceived by the ancient Egyptians at roughly between 50000 to 40000 BC.

³¹ See ASSMANN, 2005: 13 ff; 23; TOBIN, 1988: 169-183.

³² Most noticeably here cf. ALLEN, 1988; HORNUNG, 1987: 113-125; ASSMANN, 2005; DUNAND & ZIVIE–COCHE, 2004.

³³ So in fact by MORENZ, 1960: see esp. «Foreword», «Introduction»; cf. also TOBIN, 1988: 169 ff.

I.2. ANCIENT EGYPTIAN COSMOGONIES AND ARISTOTLE'S METAPHYSICS: Ancient Egyptian creation accounts have survived in a great variety of sources. Like other religious concepts they were not composed as one collective *corpus* of ideas but derive from different religious contexts, eternalized in image and writing on temple and tomb walls, papyri and even coffins³⁴. The prime sources for ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies are the Old Kingdom *Pyramid Texts* (c. 2686-2181 BC), the Middle Kingdom *Coffin Texts* (c. 2100-1650 BC), the New Kingdom *Underworld Books*, in particular the *Book of the Dead* (from c. 1550 BC onwards), *Papyrus Leiden I 350* (c. 1228 BC), the so-called *Shabaka Stone*, a black granite slab, inscribed by the XXV Dynasty King Shabaka (c. 710-701 BC), and the *Papyrus Bremner-Rhind* (BM EA 10188; c. 312-306 BC). In addition, inscriptions in numerous temples from the New Kingdom and the Helleno-Roman Period, such as the temples of Amūn-Rē^c and Khonsū in Karnak, the temples of Khnum in Esna and Elephantine and the temples of Sobek and Haroeris in Kom Ombo offer more elaborate and detailed versions of certain creation myths³⁵. These sources can be complemented by countless references to Cosmogonies in hymns to e.g.: Rē^c, Amūn, Ptah, or Aten, written on papyri or inscribed on tomb and temple walls, and stelae³⁶. Even non-religious literature *genre*, in particular instructions and lamentations, provide references to Cosmogonies³⁷. Finally, magical spells and rituals often make use of creation myths to reinforce their ritualistic power³⁸. While these sources offer numerous different Cosmogonies, a closer look reveals that most of them are variations of three major creation accounts, namely the Heliopolitan Cosmogony, the Hermopolitan Cosmogony and the Memphite Theology³⁹.

The Heliopolitan Cosmogony explains how the creator god Atūm [FIG. I] gains consciousness in the primeval waters, Nūn, and comes into being on the *primeval mound* (*bnbn*). He then self-creates the gods Shū and Tefnūt, alternatively by spitting, sneezing, or masturbating. Shū and Tefnūt mate and produce Geb (Earth) and Nūt (Sky), who after being separated by their father Shū bring about four offspring: Osiris, Isis, Seth and Nephthys. Osiris and Isis eventually produce Horus and thus create the famous *Great Ennead of Heliopolis* (*Psd̄t-ntrw ʿ3t nt Iwnw*). As Horus becomes the first legitimate heir to the throne on Earth after his father Osiris had been murdered by his brother Seth [FIG. II], the Heliopolitan Ennead can be understood as a propagandistic legitimization for the quasi-divine rulership of the Pharaoh, who is perceived as the continuous reincarnation of Horus' *k3* upon Earth⁴⁰.

The Hermopolitan Cosmogony likewise originates in the primeval waters, but this time the creator god arises from the Nūn in a primordial cosmic *egg* (*swht*) or *lotus flower* (*zšn*), carried by eight primordial deities in pairs of four gods and goddesses respectively, which represent the aspects of the chaotic primeval waters: Nūn and Naūnet (watery abyss), Heh and Hehuet (chaos, formlessness), Kek and Kekuet (darkness) and Amūn and Amaūnet (hiddenness)⁴¹. In

³⁴ See SHAFER, 1991: 90 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 44 ff.

³⁵ See n. 34, *supra*; for the Cosmogonies of Esna and Edfu see esp. FINNESTAD, 1985.

³⁶ See n. 35, *supra*; for hymns and prayers cf. especially ASSMANN, 1999.

³⁷ So for example *The Instruction for Merykare*, *The Prophecies of Neferti* and *The Admonitions of Ipuwer*; for an English translation see SIMPSON *et al.*, ²1973: 180-92, 234-40 and 210-29, respectively. On these ancient Egyptian *Sapientia* texts, see also the paper by Dr Maravelia in the present volume, namely pp. 65-68, *supra*.

³⁸ See e.g.: PINCH, 2006: esp. 1-32; BORGHOUTS, ³1978.

³⁹ These names were applied by modern Scholars according to the presumed historical origin of these Cosmogonies referred to in the respective texts. See also n. 35, *supra*. For a summary of the following Cosmogonies, see SHAFER, 1991: 90-96. On the *Shabaka Stone*, see ΧΕΛΙΩΤΗΣ, 1971.

⁴⁰ See n. 39, *supra*.

⁴¹ Depending on the source, Amūn could be replaced by Tenem, and Heh by Neheh; see e.g.: SHAFER, 1991: 94-95; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCH, 2004: 49. However, cf. also ZIVIE, 2009: 167-225.

their crudest forms the Heliopolitan and Hermopolitan Cosmogonies are already present in the *Pyramid* and *Coffin Texts* and belong thus to the oldest Cosmogonies of ancient Egypt⁴².

FIGURE II: Seth (in his other conjugate aspect of cosmic duality, i.e.: as a benevolent deity and follower of Rē/šmsw R') vanquishing 'Apophis at the prow of the cosmic bark of the solar god Rē–Horakhty and restoring Ma'at. Detail of a painting from the *Book of the Dead* of Horuben (XXI Dynasty, Egyptian Museum in Cairo, № 133).

The Memphite Theology differs from the other two, in that it unites the primeval ocean and mound with the person of the creator god Ptah himself who subsequently creates the other deities «through this heart and this tongue» i.e.: by contemplating his creation and bringing them into existence by the power of speech⁴³. By considering the Heliopolitan Ennead as part of Ptah's creation, the danger of two seemingly opposing creation accounts was once again avoided⁴⁴. Unlike the Heliopolitan and Hermopolitan Cosmogonies, the Memphite theology only survives inscribed on the *Shabaka Stone*, which states that it was copied from an earlier, worm-eaten papyrus. For decades, Egyptologists have dated the original composition of this Cosmogony to the Old Kingdom, but certain internal features of the text, such as the syncretism of Ptah with the primeval mound Tathenen as Ptah–Tathenen (which did not occur before the New Kingdom), indicate the time of Ramses II as the earliest possible date of origin⁴⁵. Ptah however was a prominent deity long before the XIX Dynasty. In the Old Kingdom he was the local god of the very ancient town of Memphis, and from at least the Middle Kingdom onwards he was the patron deity of craftsmen and artisans⁴⁶. *Coffin Texts* [Spell 647, II: 221-23] describe Ptah as a fertility god, «the one who makes vegetation grow», a role further supported by his representation as a mummified man, which links him with rebirth and resurrection in the afterlife⁴⁷. Considering these three features of a major local deity, a crafter god and a deity associated with fertility and rebirth, it is possible that the Memphite Theology was already known in the Old and Middle Kingdom, even though no conclusive source to confirm this has survived⁴⁸. For the following study these three basic Cosmogonies will consti-

⁴² See e.g.: *PT*, 301: 90; *PT*, 600: 246-47; *CT*, 76, I: 77-80; see also SHAFER, 1991: 91-95.

⁴³ See ALLEN, 1988: 38-47; SHAFER, 1991: 95 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 57 ff.

⁴⁴ See n. 43, *supra*.

⁴⁵ See ALLEN, 1988: 43; FINNESTAD, 1976: 81-113; ΧΕΛΙΩΤΗΣ, 1971: 15-16.

⁴⁶ See BONNET, 2000, 614-19: art. «Ptah»; ALLEN, 1988: 38-47.

⁴⁷ See n. 46, *supra*.

⁴⁸ See ALLEN, 1988: 38 ff; FINNESTAD, 1976: 81-113; ΧΕΛΙΩΤΗΣ, 1971: 16 ff.

tute the sample chosen from ancient Egypt, based primarily on sources from the Old through Middle Kingdom (that is, the *Pyramid* and *Coffin Texts*), with the exception of the *Shabaka Stone* inscriptions⁴⁹. Where deemed necessary sources from later periods will be also employed, in order to complement the earlier material.

Metaphysics, Aristotle's first major work on Philosophy, on the other hand, coined the name and subject matter for generations of philosophers to come⁵⁰. This famous title however was not given by Aristotle himself [FIG. VI], but was applied by a 1st Century AD Scholar from Alexandria, who arranged what were mere lecture notes of Aristotle into specific volumes. *Meta-Physics*, literally: «after the Physics», likely indicated the position in a philosophical curriculum, which presupposed the scientific axioms treated in Aristotle's *Physics*⁵¹. Aristotle himself called this treatise «The Study of Being qua Being», or «First Philosophy» that is the «wisdom [that] deal[s] with the first causes and the principles of things»⁵². According to Aristotle these principles, which are the most fundamental ones, seem very abstract and distant to Scholars at first. Thus, in order to reach knowledge of these first principles, the Scholar has to develop from things «which are more knowable and obvious to [him]» to «things that are clearer and more knowable by nature»⁵³. Therefore, a great deal of *Metaphysics* is occupied with analyzing the things «knowable relatively to us», and as they clearly exist, they have to be studied as beings in so far as they *are*⁵⁴.

Since «there are many senses in which a thing may be said to be» Aristotle distinguishes between primary beings or «substances», which «are not predicated of a subject, but everything else is predicated of them», and nine secondary beings or qualities that classify a substance and cannot exist apart from it⁵⁵. Since substances are such fundamental beings, Aristotle next endeavours into their nature⁵⁶. After a lengthy, confusing and often even contradictory discussion of this subject matter — which cannot be treated in details here — Aristotle derives the conclusion that all substances are essentially hylomorphic compounds, that is compounds made of matter and form, both of which pre-exist eternally⁵⁷. In merely formal objects, for example the geometrical concept of a circle, the substantial matter can be substituted by intelligible matter⁵⁸. As for «all things which have no [substantial or intelligible] matter» they are «without any qualifications, essentially unities»⁵⁹. In a hylomorphic compound the form (or idea, or image in the mind) is the reason why a particular thing is in fact an *actual* entity, whereas the matter has the mere potential to embody the form⁶⁰. The nature and origin, as well as

⁴⁹ The applied texts for this paper derive from the following translations: FAULKNER, 1969 (for the *PT*, where after the Spell follow the pages); FAULKNER, 1973-78 (for the *CT*, where after the Spell, follow the respective volume of Faulkner's translation I-III [not of DE BUCK!] and then the pages). For the Memphite Theology, see ALLEN, 1988: 43-44.

⁵⁰ See BARNES, 1995: 1-26; ALLAN, 1970: 1-22.

⁵¹ See BARNES, 1995: 6 ff.

⁵² See *Metaphysics*, I.1: 689-91. The text samples chosen for this paper derive from the comprehensive translation by MCKEON, 2001, and will be abbreviated as follows: philosophical work; number of the book of this work; chapter in the book; page number in the translation. They are based primarily on Aristotle's *Metaphysics*, but will be complemented from other philosophical works of Aristotle, where deemed necessary.

⁵³ See *Metaphysics*, VII.3: 784-86; *Physics*, I.1: 218 ff.

⁵⁴ See *Physics*, I.1: 218 ff; see also BARNES, 1995: 69 ff; ALLAN, 1970: 70 ff.

⁵⁵ See *Metaphysics*, IV.2: 732 ff; *Metaphysics*, V.7: 760-62; beings according to Aristotle include *both, animate and inanimate entities*, e.g.: animals and plants but also wooden tables and bronze statues, & c.; see e.g.: *Physics*, I: 218-36.

⁵⁶ See *Metaphysics*, IV: 731-51; VII: 783-811; VIII: 811-20; IX: 820-34.

⁵⁷ See *Metaphysics*, VIII.6: 818-20; see also: BARNES, 1995: 77 ff; ALLAN, 1970: 73 ff.

⁵⁸ See e.g.: *Metaphysics*, VII.12: 803 ff; VIII.6: 818-20.

⁵⁹ See *Metaphysics*, VIII.6: 820.

⁶⁰ See *Metaphysics*, VII.3: 784-86; BARNES, 1995: 78 ff.

the change underlying any composite substance can be explained in four steps, or four causes: the *material cause* (matter), the *formal cause* (form, idea), the *efficient* or *moving cause* (the event of producing the form–matter compound) and the *final cause* or *purpose* (the completed or desired substance)⁶¹. However this process of change cannot go on infinitely, and at one point Aristotle supposes an eternal, purely formal substance, which moves (i.e.: causes or changes) everything else but is itself unmoved (uncaused)⁶². Knowing this ultimate first principle is the aim of *Metaphysics*, but Aristotle stresses very early in his treatise that this is impossible. He calls the study of *being qua being* a divine science as it is ultimately concerned with the *Divine* (the *Unmoved Mover*), but only this divine being can understand and know the subject matter of this science completely⁶³. But since the study of *Metaphysics* brings the «lover of wisdom» closer to divine knowledge, the «first Philosophy» is worth pursuing⁶⁴. In the following study we shall compare the three most important concepts of Aristotle's *Metaphysics*, namely the *Four Causes*, the nature of the *Unmoved Mover* and the *Concept of Actuality and Potentiality*, to the three major creation accounts of ancient Egypt, namely the Heliopolitan, Hermopolitan and Memphite Cosmogonies, in order to demonstrate that the *roots* (ρίζωματα) of early Aristotelian ideas can already be found in ancient Egyptian creation accounts. **This study does not intend to show that Aristotle borrowed and developed his ideas from these creation accounts**, but rather attempts to point out that **the ancient Egyptians indeed possessed a rational understanding of abstraction**, albeit hidden under the surface of metaphysical allegories and their archetypal mytho–theological symbolism⁶⁵.

II. ARISTOTELIAN CAUSALITY IN ANCIENT EGYPTIAN COSMOGONIES

In *Metaphysics*, Aristotle attempts to gain a profound understanding of the world of substances around him. According to him this can only be accomplished if the Philosopher knows its causes⁶⁶. Both in *Physics* and *Metaphysics* Aristotle gives a detailed account of these four causes, which can offer an explanation to the question why something is the way it is⁶⁷. It is noteworthy to remark here, that Aristotle was not the first person to apply causes to explain the world. In fact, in *Metaphysics* [I.3-10: 693-712], Aristotle highlights the errors of fellow philosophers who were able to pinpoint to some of these four causes, but whose lack of a concept of causality prevented a rational and meaningful outcome. Despite the careful distinction into Four Causes, Aristotle frequently reminds his Scholars, that a cause can be used in more than one sense to explain the same thing, and indeed formal, essential and final cause often overlap⁶⁸. The explanation offered by these four causes is a teleological one, that is an explanation whose frame of reference is the *telos* (τέλος), or purpose of a thing⁶⁹. According to Aristotle [FIG. V] this purpose can be achieved in two different ways: by means of artistic creation or

⁶¹ See *Physics*, II.3: 240-42; *Metaphysics*, V.2: 752-54.

⁶² See *Metaphysics*, I.2: 692-93; II.2: 713-15; XII: 872-88.

⁶³ See *Metaphysics*, III: 715-31.

⁶⁴ See n. 63, *supra*; BARNES, 1995: 66 ff; ALLAN, 1970: 70 ff.

⁶⁵ Prof. James Allen (cf. ALLEN, 1988) makes frequent reference and comparisons to «causes» which are clearly based on Aristotle, even though he does not mention him by name. However, Allen does not strictly pursue this causality, as it supports, but does not make up the subject matter of his work.

⁶⁶ See *AnaPost*, I.1-2: 110-13.

⁶⁷ See n. 62, *supra*. Such an explanation can only be given for complex (compound) entities, for simple substances or axioms are universal truths and therefore self–explanatory; cf. BARNES, 1995: 71 ff; 101 ff.

⁶⁸ See *Physics*, II.7: 247-48; *De Anima*, II.4: 561 ff.

⁶⁹ See GOTTHELF, 1976: 226-54.

production and by means of natural generation⁷⁰. The former explains for example the origin of a bronze statue. The material cause of this statue is, of course, the bronze; its formal cause is the image of the statue in the mind of the craftsman; the efficient cause is the combining of matter and form in order to create the final cause or purpose, the bronze statue⁷¹. The second way describes the natural generation of animals and plants, as exemplified in Aristotle's famous phrase of a human who begets another human⁷². In this case the material and the formal cause of a new generation are innate in the parent(s), the essential cause is the force of nature, i.e.: intercourse and conception in animals, and fecundation in plants, paired with an inherent strive or desire towards a given, natural *telos*, and the final cause is of course the matured being⁷³. In the ancient Egyptian creation accounts this causality is doubtlessly present, as shall be highlighted below.

II.1. THE MATERIAL CAUSE: According to Aristotle, the material cause is «that out of which a thing comes to be and which persists», in other words the matter out of which something is created⁷⁴. Aristotle stresses that «matter pre-exist[s]» and is not generated when a compound substance is created. According to him, matter does not come into being or perishes, it merely undergoes changes⁷⁵. Aristotle perceives matter as pure potentiality, which has the potential to become an actual entity only by means of this entity's essence, its form⁷⁶. He distinguishes between two different types of matter: physical and intelligible. The former is matter in its most literal form, the physical substance that is able to become actualized. Aristotle elaborates that this *prima materia*⁷⁷ can only exist actualized in either of one of the four simple, elemental substances; air, fire, water and earth. These elements exist independently from an Unmoved Mover (see *infra*), and can change into each other⁷⁸. Intelligible matter on the other hand is a product of thought, introduced by Aristotle to provide a quasi-material for purely geometrical and mind-existent entities (~ *thought-forms*), in order to be able to define them (as only hylomorphic compounds can be defined), and thus be able to explain their purpose by means of the Four Causes⁷⁹.

Both in the Cosmogonies of Heliopolis and Hermopolis the material cause appears as a two-fold matter. The most obvious and persistent one is the primeval water, from which the creator god originated and eventually arose⁸⁰. This primeval watery mass is called Nūn (*Nwn*) and was present «[...] before the sky existed, before earth existed, before humans existed, before the gods were born, before death existed»⁸¹. It therefore subsists eternally as «prime matter» or mere potentiality, ready to be changed and made actual. The second case of matter derives from the primeval water in various ways. In the Heliopolitan tradition, the Demiurge (Atūm or even Atūm-Khepri) rises from the primeval water on a primordial mound, or the *bnbn*-sto-

⁷⁰ See *Physics*, II.1: 236 ff; *Metaphysics*, V.2: 753 ff; VII.7: 791-93.

⁷¹ See n. 70, *supra*; BARNES, 1995: 101 ff.

⁷² See n. 71, *supra*.

⁷³ See n. 71, *supra*; BARNES, 1995: 101-08; ALLAN, 1970: 70-78.

⁷⁴ See *Physics*, II.3: 240-42.

⁷⁵ See e.g.: *Metaphysics*, VII.3: 784-86.

⁷⁶ See *Metaphysics*, VII: 783-811; IX: 820-34.

⁷⁷ Aristotle never actually uses the term *prima materia*, but his description in *Metaphysics*, VII.3: 785 ff clearly indicates such a concept. For a more detailed discussion on *prime matter*, see ROBINSON, 1974: 168-88; FINE, 1992: 35-57.

⁷⁸ See *De Cælo*, I.1: 398-428; *Metaphysics*, IX: 820-34.

⁷⁹ See *Metaphysics*, VII: 11 ff; 800 ff; FINE, 1992: 35-57; BARNES, 1995: 95 ff.

⁸⁰ See e.g.: *PT*, 222: 49 ff; *PT*, 600: 246 ff; *CT*, 714, II: 270.

⁸¹ See *PT*, 571: 226; see also: ASSMANN, 2005: 14 ff; cf. also BICKEL, 1994: 33 ff; 72 ff.

ne⁸². The origin of the first mound marks the creation of a separate, elemental part of prime matter, namely Earth in addition to Water. The same context also alludes to a third form of matter, for it says that Atūm «spat out Shū... [and] expectorated Tefnūt» or created them by means of self-insemination⁸³. The bodily fluids of the Demiurge doubtlessly describe the matter necessary for natural generation, whereas Nūn and the primeval mound constitute the primal material cause, such as the pristine material for artistic creation⁸⁴. In the Hermopolitan Cosmogony the Heliopolitan primeval mound is substituted by a primordial egg or lotus which hatched or revealed the creator god⁸⁵. Here, too, a different matter developed from prime matter to generate the Demiurge. It is important to keep in mind that the elemental deities were not only independent divinities, but at the same time symbolized the elements upon the Earth⁸⁶. In contrast to Aristotle the four material elements: *air/aër*, *fire/ignis*, *water/aqua* and *earth/terra*, have not persisted eternally in ancient Egyptian thought, but gradually developed from the primeval water⁸⁷. Shū (*Air*, Αἰθήρ) and Tefnūt (*Moisture*, Ὑδωρ)⁸⁸, such as their children Geb (*Earth*, Γαῖα) and Nūt (*Sky*, Οὐρανός) can be interpreted as the four material elements, that together with the Sun god (*Fire/Light*, Πῦρ/Φῶς), usually the creator god himself, constitute the matter of the ordered world of the living. The ambiguity of ancient Egyptian religion, however, makes it difficult to apply the Aristotelian Philosophy in this case.

The Memphite Theology offers quite a different type of matter. As mentioned above, Ptah «gave life to all the gods and their *k3w* [...] through [his] heart and [his] tongue»⁸⁹. This alludes to Aristotle's hylomorphic compound of form and intelligible matter, both pre-existing in the mind⁹⁰. However, since the Memphite Theology combines the creation myth of Ptah with the ancient Heliopolitan Cosmogony, physical matter appears alongside and in fact *before* intelligible one. Ptah is said to have arisen from the primeval ocean Ptah-Nūn and Ptah-Naūnet (MATTER 1), on the primeval mound «Ta-thenen [...] who gave birth to the gods» (MATTER 2), in order to create the subsequent gods and the world as such by means of intelligible matter (MATTER 3)⁹¹. The latter can be interpreted as a variation of Atūm's bodily fluids which triggered generation.

II.2. THE FORMAL CAUSE: Once the material cause is given a formal counterpart is required. According to Aristotle the formal cause is «the form [...] the [account] of essence», or differently put that what makes a substance this very substance⁹². Unlike the material cause, the formal cause pre-exists eternally. In case of production the formal cause constitutes the idea in the artisan's mind; in terms of generation it is naturally innate in the parent⁹³. Often the formal cause overlaps with the efficient cause, for it is the idea in the head that eventually initiates the embodiment of this idea in matter⁹⁴. In contrast to the material cause, the formal cause

⁸² See *PT*, 600: 246-47; PINCH, 2003: 180-81; BONNET, 32000, 847-48: art. «Urhügel».

⁸³ See *PT*, 600: 246-47; *PT*, 527: 198; *PT*, 660: 271; see also *CT*, 75, I: 72-77; *CT*, 76, I: 77-80; *CT*, 80, I: 83-87.

⁸⁴ See ALLEN, 1988: 13 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 55 ff.

⁸⁵ See *PT*, 249: 60-61; *CT*, 75, I: 72-77, *CT*, 80, I: 83-87.

⁸⁶ See HORNUNG, 2005: 62 ff; see also Section III, *infra*.

⁸⁷ See esp. *CT*, 75-80, I: 72-87; ALLEN, 1988: 27 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 45 ff, 55 ff; ASSMANN, 2005: 14 ff.

⁸⁸ See ASSMANN, 2005: 15 ff; BICKEL, 1994: 169 ff; and in parts also BONNET, 32000, 771-74: art. «Tefnūt», who doubts that Tefnūt should be interpreted as moisture, but proposes «fire» as her element instead.

⁸⁹ See ALLEN, 1988: 3-4, 43.

⁹⁰ See n. 80, *supra*.

⁹¹ See ALLEN, 1988: 38 ff; ASSMANN, 2005: 24 ff.

⁹² See *Physics*, II.3; 240 ff.

⁹³ See *Metaphysics*, V.2: 752 ff; cf. also, BARNES, 1995: 148 ff; ALLAN, 1970: 31 ff, 71, 86 ff.

⁹⁴ See n. 69, *supra*.

is pure actuality. It does not contain any material elements and is therefore absolutely simple, unchangeable and universal⁹⁵.

In the Heliopolitan and Hermopolitan Cosmogonies, the first formal cause coincides with the self-realization of the Demiurge in the primeval waters, consisting of the first instance of *actuality*. Previously the creator god, Atūm, subsisted in a state of *inertia* (*nnwt*) in the primeval ocean, until the moment of the *first occasion* (*zp tpy*), when Atūm manifested (or developed) himself. This self-realization and self-development was personified in the *Pyramid Texts* as Atūm-Khepri: Atūm, who comes into being⁹⁶. The ancient Egyptians rarely specified how exactly this moment took place, but merely explained that it did. One version states that Atūm gained self-consciousness after a dialogue with the primeval water which advises him to: «kiss [his] daughter [Tefnūt], put her at [his] nose [so that his] heart may live»⁹⁷. However, the context reveals that this event should be placed between the *first occasion* and the creation of the physical world. The self-realizing actuality of the Creator combined with the primeval matter, in which the Demiurge was present only potentially, triggered the first hylomorphic compound: Atūm⁹⁸. The nature of this event can be interpreted as self-generation. The subsequent origin of Shū and Tefnūt, too, was a generational process, the formal cause now being innate in Atūm. Atūm therefore was virtually the first formal cause, both primarily as he formed himself at the *first occasion*, and secondarily as he «made every [other] form alone»⁹⁹. The Memphite Theology offers a different angle. After the *first occasion*, Ptah actively created the world around him, in contrast to the Heliopolitan and Hermopolitan Cosmogonies whose development is a matter of generation¹⁰⁰. It is Ptah's heart that «[caused] every conclusion to emerge»¹⁰¹. The image in the mind of the divine artisan made up the entirety of the gods and the land. These formal principles were actualized as compound substances through the primordial matter of Ptah-Nūn and Ptah-Tathenen, or as abstract principles by means of intelligible matter¹⁰².

II.3. THE EFFICIENT CAUSE: The fusion of the material and formal causes constitutes Aristotle's efficient cause, or the «primary source of change or rest»¹⁰³. Once again Aristotle distinguishes between efficient causes in generation and artistic production. However, this distinction is not as sharply marked as with the previous two causes. In both cases the efficient cause is innate in the knowledge on how to *cause* specific things. It is, thus, not the craftsman who causes the image of the statue to materialize in bronze-matter, but the knowledge of craftsmanship that acts as the efficient or moving cause¹⁰⁴. Aristotle here distinguishes between «general causes for general things and particular causes of particular things», which means that usually the efficient cause for production is the knowledge of craftsmanship: the artist's process. In case of a particular statue, however, this knowledge can be complemented by the artist's individual skills and techniques¹⁰⁵. Similarly, the human who begets another human is

⁹⁵ See e.g.: *Metaphysics*, VII: 783 ff.

⁹⁶ See *PT*, 600: 246-47; *PT*, 222: 49-51; *CT*, 75-81, I: 72-87; cf. also ALLEN, 1988: 14-27; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 47 ff; COHN, 1993: 5 ff.

⁹⁷ See *CT*, 80, I: 83-87.

⁹⁸ See ALLEN, 1988: 24 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 48 ff; ASSMANN, 1995A: 167 ff.

⁹⁹ See *pBremner-Rhind*: l. 14 in ALLEN, 1988, 28; cf. also *op. cit.*: 29 ff.

¹⁰⁰ See e.g.: ASSMANN, 2005: 30-34.

¹⁰¹ See ALLEN, 1988: 18 ff, 43 ff.

¹⁰² See esp. SHAFER, 1991: 96 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 56-58; ASSMANN, 2005: 24-30.

¹⁰³ See *Physics*, II.3: 241; *Metaphysics*, V.2: 752 ff.

¹⁰⁴ See *Physics*, II.3: 242 ff.

¹⁰⁵ See *Physics*, II.3: 241 ff.

not the moving cause of this natural process, but the knowledge how to do so is¹⁰⁶. Efficient causes cannot always be distinguished from formal and final causes, and often «form, mover and *telos* [final cause] coincide», especially in the case of natural generation¹⁰⁷. The form of a grown, matured human is at the same time the cause of its movement (its natural growth) and eventually its final purpose¹⁰⁸.

A similar idea appears in the ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies. Two distinguished essential causes derive from the sources, i.e.: Ma^cat and Heka¹⁰⁹. Ma^cat can best be paralleled with Aristotle's efficient cause of natural generation, the «natural knowledge of the ordered world»¹¹⁰. In fact, Ma^cat is precisely that. As initially mentioned, Ma^cat describes among others the principle of Cosmic Order, and it is in this notion that Ma^cat corresponds to an efficient cause. The *Coffin Texts* [Spells 78, I: 81ff and 80, I: 83ff] describe how Order came into existence at the moment of creation. Accordingly, Atūm's daughter Tefnūt is identified with the cosmic principle of order, alongside her brother Shū who represents the life cycle. Both deities were generated out of Atūm and only their appearance made the creation of the physical world possible¹¹¹. It is thus Order that determines the rightful formation of subsequent generation. It will also remain as the underlying natural principle of the physical world that determines the periodic cycles of all the celestial bodies, the annual inundation and consequently the piety and the righteous deeds of humans¹¹². But Ma^cat did not only create an ordered Universe, she also brought about time, the repeated cycle of eternal sameness *dt* [see § III.1]. The idea of Ma^cat as efficient cause raises two problems. Did Order as an efficient cause only begin to exist after the creation of Shū and Tefnūt? Or are Shū and Tefnūt merely parts of Atūm, as Atūm was part of the Nūn, and thus did not strictly require an underlying natural order for generation? The latter can be interpreted either way from the same sources. On the one hand, it was Atūm who created Shū and Tefnūt by means of sneezing and spitting. On the other hand they continued to live not only with him, but as parts of him at «[his] back and his [belly]»¹¹³. The ancient Egyptian ambiguity of perceiving things once again seems to make it impossible to directly apply Aristotle's Philosophy [FIG. V].

However, there is a different approach, namely the second efficient cause *Heka* (*Hk3*). This term is commonly translated as *Magic*, but its connotation includes so much more than the modern term indicates. It is not only a means of ritual spells and witchcraft, but also the driving, immanent, creating force of the natural and supernatural spheres¹¹⁴. In fact, anything that «produces an effect can be thought of having this force»¹¹⁵. *Coffin Texts* [Spell 261, I: 199-201] allude that it was by means of *Heka* that Atūm created Shū, who then took on this abstract element¹¹⁶. But it was likewise *Heka* «who made the god [Atūm] functional»¹¹⁷. The texts also refer to one of two components of *Heka*: Hu or *Authoritative Utterance* (Hu/*Hw* is frequen-

¹⁰⁶ See e.g.: *Physics*, II.2: 240; *De Part. Animal.*, I: 643-58; *Metaphysics*, VII.7: 792-95.

¹⁰⁷ See n. 69, *supra*.

¹⁰⁸ See *Physics*, II.8: 249 ff; see also GOTTHELF, 1976: 226-54.

¹⁰⁹ See ALLEN, 1988: 36-38; ASSMANN, 1994: 167 ff.

¹¹⁰ See *AnaPost*, I: 110 ff; *De Part. Animal.*, I.1: 643 ff; and in parts *De Caelo*, I: 398 ff.

¹¹¹ See esp. *CT*, 80, I: 84 ff.

¹¹² See ASSMANN, 1994: esp. 160 ff.

¹¹³ See *CT*, 80, I: 83-87; see also ALLEN, 1988: 21 ff.

¹¹⁴ See e.g.: PINCH, 2006: 10 ff; BONNET, ³2000, 435-39: art. «Magie»; ALLEN, 1988: 36-38.

¹¹⁵ See ALLEN, 1988: 37. Cf. also MARAVELIA, 2006: Chapter V, § 1.5.

¹¹⁶ Cf. the Utterance «Becoming Heka» in *CT*, 261, I: 199-201.

¹¹⁷ Translation based here on ALLEN, 1988, 37: l. 19.

tly mentioned in combination with Sia/Si3, Perception)¹¹⁸. It is what the mind perceives and the mouth announces that becomes reality. Thus, Atūm first «became effective in his heart»¹¹⁹, and consequently developed himself and others through «Utterance (Hu) who speaks in darkness»¹²⁰. As Hu and Sia constitute Heka, it is indeed this force that best parallels the first efficient cause of creation, followed by a combination of the principles of Heka and Maꜥat which act as the efficient cause of everything else that would come into being¹²¹.

While Heka and Maꜥat are mentioned in particular in the Heliopolitan and Hermopolitan Cosmogonies, the same concept applies to the Memphite Theology. When Ptah uses his «tongue [Annunciation] [to] repeat what the heart [Perception] plans» in order to create the components of the world, he is applying *Heka* while relying on the underlying force of Maꜥat¹²². In this case, formal and efficient, but also material causes, in form of intelligible matter [see II.1] coincide.

II.4. THE FINAL CAUSE: The outcome of the pooling of matter and form by means of the efficient cause is the purpose of a thing, or its final cause. The final cause is «the *end* (lit.: *purpose/telos*) [or] that for which a thing is done»¹²³. In that example of the craftsman producing a bronze statue this bronze statue is the final cause or purpose. By taking the end, the *telos*, as a frame of reference Aristotle offers what is called a *teleological explanation* both for artistic production and natural generation¹²⁴. The *telos* of artistic production is essentially a mirror image of, but not precisely the same as, the formal cause. The latter is the pre-existing, universal blueprint in the crafter's mind — which only when materialized in physical matter — can become the final statue. The *telos* can thus be perceived as a fingerprint of the formal cause¹²⁵.

The case of natural generation requires more elaboration. According to Aristotle everything in nature strives for what is believed to be its most perfect and most suitable form¹²⁶. On a small scale this explains why a «human always begets a human», that is why human beings repeat a certain form, despite individual variations¹²⁷. So also the growth of an oak-tree out of an acorn occurs due to this natural strive¹²⁸. This innate desire aims to explain the physical and mental differences in living substances whose bodies possess or lack certain qualities for their best possible, natural adaptation¹²⁹. On a broader scale, Aristotle uses this very argumentation to explain the origins and nature of the world in teleological terms¹³⁰. For reasons that will be elaborated later, Aristotle perceives the divine supremacy (God) as a living but purely

¹¹⁸ See e.g.: PT, 255: 66; PT, 257: 67; CT, 261, I: 199-201; 335^{I-II}, I: 260-69; 1128, III: 166; cf. also: BONNET, ³2000, 318-20: art. «Hu»; *op. cit.*, 715: art. «Sia».

¹¹⁹ See *pBremner-Rhind* in ALLEN, 1988: 28-29.

¹²⁰ See CT, 1136, III: 173; CT, 320, I: 248-49.

¹²¹ See also ASSMANN, 1995: 167 ff; BONNET, ³2000, 864-67: art. «Weltbeginn».

¹²² See ALLEN, 1988: 19, 43; Earlier sources support the use of Heka in the creation through Ptah: cf. e.g.: CT, 647, II: 221-23: «Protection in Ptah» refers to the god as having «Utterance in his mouth and Perception in his Belly», and a Ramesside Papyrus identifies him as «Magic that has control of the gods» (Berlin: *Hymn to Ptah*), as translated in ALLEN, 1988: 40 ff; see also: FINNESTAD, 1976: 85 ff.

¹²³ See *Physics*, II.3: 241; *Metaphysics*, V.2: 752 ff.

¹²⁴ See GOTTHELF, 1976: 226-54. Could the final creation of divine images by Ptah be compared to the *final cause*?

¹²⁵ See BARNES, 1995: 120 ff, 127 ff; ALLAN, 1970: 85 ff; see also n. 124, *supra*; finally, cf. *Physics*, II.6: 247 ff.

¹²⁶ See esp. *Physics*, II.8: 249.

¹²⁷ See GOTTHELF, 1976: 229 ff.

¹²⁸ See e.g.: *Metaphysics*, IX.8: 828 ff.

¹²⁹ See *Physics*, II.8: 249; *Metaphysics*, IX.8: 828 ff.

¹³⁰ See GOTTHELF, 1976: 235 ff; BARNES, 1995: 127 ff.

formal, and thus ultimately simple and unchangeable, in short, perfect being. Consequently all compound beings aspire towards this pure perfection by nature. However due to the deficiency of matter which, as mere potentiality can be formed to the better or worse, they can only approach –but never achieve– this perfection themselves¹³¹.

On the other hand, Aristotle argues that every living being is subjected to a natural strive, including even the most perfect one. The only thing fitting to be desired by a purely perfect being, however, is itself. Consequently, the nature of existence is –according to Aristotle– the *telos* of an ultimate perfect and immaterial being¹³². This desire for the best possible outcome is also present in artistic production, for only something that resembles perfection as closely as possible makes the artist happy, and according to Aristotle *εὐδαιμονία* (= *happiness and good luck by God*) and *εὖ ζεῖν* (= *living well*) which increase the closer a being approaches *perfection* (*τελειότης*), designate the prime desire of every conscious being¹³³. Finally, it is noteworthy to mention that Aristotle did not presuppose a *telos* for every single substance in the Universe. Natural phenomena, such as rain or solar and lunar eclipses, do not pursue a specific purpose according to him¹³⁴. In this case it is the efficient cause, that offers an explanation for the question why a substance is the way it is¹³⁵.

FIGURE III: 1. [LEFT]: The killing of an evil serpent and of the unholy ass, symbols of ‘Apophis and Seth, respectively. Detail from the *Book of the Dead* of Kenna (late XVIII Dynasty, RMO of Leiden, № SR).
2. [RIGHT]: The justified deceased ready to slaughter the unholy, evil and virtually threatening crocodiles in the hereafter. Detail from the *Book of the Dead* of Nakht (XVIII Dynasty, British Museum, № EA 10471).

The *telos* or final cause is less obvious in ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies. While sources frequently refer to *how* and *in what way* the world was created they do not give a distinct purpose¹³⁶. Since this seems to rule out artistic production immediately¹³⁷, the only remaining *telos* is that of natural generation and aspiration to the best possible outcome. Indeed, a natural generation in creation accounts has already been revealed (while analyzing the previous three causes). Atūm gained consciousness in the Nūn and brought about Shū and Tefnūt by means of natural generation, who then continued this process. But with the appearance of Shū and Tefnūt,

¹³¹ See *Metaphysics*, XII: 872-88, esp. XII.6: 877 ff; see also DEFILIPPO, 1994: 393-409. [EDITOR’S NOTE: Cf. also the «definition» of *art* (*hmt*) from the wisdom of Ptah-hotep in *pPrisse*, 5, ll 9-10: *n in.tw drw hmt, nn hmww ꜥpr 3hw.f*].

¹³² See DEFILIPPO, 1994: 395 ff; GOTTHELF, 1976: 226 ff; cf. also ALLAN, 1970: 86-96.

¹³³ See *Nicomachian Ethics*, I.7: 941 ff.

¹³⁴ See *Metaphysics*, VIII.4: 816 ff.

¹³⁵ The efficient cause in this case would be considered its primary cause. For Aristotle’s hierarchy of causes within the causality of things, see *Metaphysics*, V.11: 763 ff; IX.7: 828 ff; cf. also BARNES, 1995: 105 ff, 127 ff.

¹³⁶ See e.g.: PLUMLEY, 1975: 17 ff; HORNUNG, 2005: 150 ff.

¹³⁷ As the formal idea of a planned outcome, similar to the *Genesis* of the *Bible*, would have been very likely mentioned in context, see ASSMANN, 2005: 30-34.

Atūm also created Life and Order, which determined the nature of the world and of all subsequent beings¹³⁸. This short moment of the *first occasion* between the timeless, chaotic primeval era and the creation of the physical world was a time of Ultimate Order, life and perfection, which eventually got disturbed by the introduction of evil¹³⁹ [FIG. I, III.1-2].

It was this short moment of perfect Order and Happiness that later generations attempted to imitate as closely as possible¹⁴⁰! This reenactment of the *first occasion* is present in the solar cult of the sun-god, who rises in the morning at the moment of the virtually recurring *first occasion* (*zp tpy*), and consequently in the reign of every new king in Egypt¹⁴¹. **The re-creation of pure Ma'at and happiness/perfection/beauty (*nfrw*) is the subject matter of ancient Egyptian religion, Science and even daily life affairs and rituals**¹⁴². It can therefore be concluded that Atūm fused with Order and Life constituted the purest and most desirable perfection. In contrast to Aristotle, this perfect moment and being (the creator god Atūm), which every living being naturally aspires, is a hylomorphic substance made of eternal matter and form¹⁴³.

Actually, Atūm himself desires it, too. *Book of the Dead* Spell 175 proves to be a valuable source for deducing the purpose of creation. While it does not explicitly state a reason for the creation of the world, it offers an explanation for its ultimate destruction. The spell describes how Atūm and Osiris grow weary of the disorder and injustice at the end of the world. Consequently, Atūm decides to «destroy everything [he] created [so that] this land will return to the state of Nūn [...] as was its original condition»¹⁴⁴. Only he himself and Osiris will remain in it eternally unified in the form of a serpent «that humans cannot know and gods cannot see»¹⁴⁵. This passage alludes to the ultimate inability to restore the aspired moment of the *first occasion* and prefers a timeless, lifeless and chaotic existence to the deficiency of the world¹⁴⁶. It can be deduced that due to this deficient state Atūm's natural aspiration cannot be met.

Such a case would not, of course, occur in Aristotle's Philosophy as it is the Unmoved Mover who defines the world as his own aspiration by desiring it. However, it is necessary to remember that Aristotle presupposes a simple, purely actual, and thus absolutely flawless being as his Unmoved Mover, whereas the ancient Egyptian Prime Mover at the state of the *first occasion* is already a compound substance of eternal potentiality and of actuality. The deficiency of the world which ultimately corrupts the Demiurge's self-aspiration derives from this very eternal potentiality and can thus explain the apparent contradiction¹⁴⁷.

In contrast to the *telos* of natural aspiration, non-religious literature sources offer a different approach. According to the Middle Kingdom *Instruction for Merykare*, it is «for the sake of Humankind that god's cattle was created», that the Creator «made sky and earth [...], subdued

¹³⁸ See *CT*, 80, I: 83-87. On Ma'at as the Cosmic Order/Law impersonate, see MARAVELIA, 2007: 1243-50.

¹³⁹ See DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 52 ff, 62 ff; ASSMANN, 1995A: 167-74; HORNUNG, 2005: 155 ff; see the related discussion with modern cosmological terms in MARAVELIA, 2006: 395, 400; cf. also Section II.4, *supra*.

¹⁴⁰ See e.g.: *PT*, 606: 250 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 52-55.

¹⁴¹ See QUIRKE, 2001: 41 ff; ASSMANN, 1995A: 174 ff.

¹⁴² See n. 141, *supra*. On beauty and perfection in the ancient Egyptian mind, see LEMBKE & SCHMITZ, 2006.

¹⁴³ See ASSMANN, 1995A: 167 ff, in parts 174 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 107 ff.

¹⁴⁴ As translated in DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 67 ff; see also: KÁKOSY, 1963: 17-30; SCHOTT, 1959: 319-30. Perhaps, as Dr Nadine Guilhou pointed out, Nūn transforms himself from *potentiality* into *actuality*.

¹⁴⁵ See *BD*: 175, (as translated in: DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 67 ff). Cf. also MARAVELIA, 2006: 397 & n. 114.

¹⁴⁶ Eschatological references to the end of the world for this reason already appear in earlier texts, such as the *Pyramid Texts*, or the *Admonitions of Ipuwer*. On this topic, see additionally Maravelia's interpretation in n. 145, *supra*.

¹⁴⁷ Since the Memphite theology combines the supremacy of Ptah with the Heliopolitan tradition, the same consideration of the *telos* applies here as well. Cf. also ALLEN, 1988: 38 ff.

the water monsters (i.e.: repelled the primeval chaos in favour of Order) [...] made for them plants and cattle [...] rulers in the egg [...] [and] magic as weapons»¹⁴⁸. The small scale *telos* in this case is the artistic creation of Humankind and the sources of their well-being. While this conception is not unparalleled in ancient Egyptian literature, the overall perception of human's place among God's other creations was in general much humbler, as is evident in particular in the solar hymns to Amūn or Aten from the New Kingdom, which place humans arbitrarily in between other living beings¹⁴⁹. In general, though, the *telos* in Old and Middle Kingdom sources was one of natural aspiration toward the best possible outcome.

II.5. EXCURSUS I: THE CREATION OF EVIL AND OF THE UNDERWORLD BY MEANS OF THE FOUR CAUSES: In actuality however, this outcome was not always as pleasant as aspired, and it did not take long for evil to come into existence. By applying Aristotle's Causality the creation of evil shall now be analyzed.

The origin and creation of evil is generally ascribed to the god Seth¹⁵⁰ [FIG. II, III.1]. *Evil* or *isft* in this sense is the direct opposite of *mꜣꜥt*. Numerous passages in the *Pyramid Texts* allude to this event, even though they give no coherent account of this process, in order to ritually avoid its re-occurrence¹⁵¹. According to these references, Seth disrupted the (until then stable) Cosmic Order in two major ways. As one of four children of the god Geb and the goddess Nūt, Seth demonstrated his power and rebellion by breaking free from his mother's side instead of being born naturally like his siblings¹⁵². In addition the birth of this second male heir (after Osiris) terminated the smooth transition of power from father to son, of the two previous generations¹⁵³. Consequently, feelings of envy and jealousy developed in Seth when his brother Osiris, the first born son, was eventually chosen to reign as king of Egypt, and ultimately erupted in the fratricide of Osiris by Seth¹⁵⁴.

In terms of causality these incidences, which disturbed the Cosmic Order and displayed Seth's deficient nature [FIG. II, III.1], were a byproduct of the natural generation of things. According to Aristotle, caused substances may themselves be causes¹⁵⁵. In this case, Seth who was the final cause of the four-fold natural generation of Geb and Nūt simultaneously became the efficient cause in the creation of disorder. But from where did Seth's evil intentions originate?

According to Aristotle [FIG. V] evil derives from a deficiency in the conscious mind, which results from the fact that all conscious beings (except the Unmoved Mover) are hylomorphic beings of an unchangeable soul, and literally formable matter, which, as previously mentioned, can be changed either for the better or for the worse¹⁵⁶. Again, Aristotle believes that the ultimate goal of every conscious living being without exception is happiness¹⁵⁷. But according to him there are agents who do not seek happiness by means of virtuous deeds, and in

¹⁴⁸ See SIMPSON *et al.*, 21973: 191. See also the Anthropic Principle's discussion in MARAVELIA, 2006: 408-09.

¹⁴⁹ See ASSMANN, 1999; HORNUNG, 1967: 69-84.

¹⁵⁰ See TE VELDE, 1967; MEURER, 2002: esp. 99-167.

¹⁵¹ For a detailed analysis on ritually avoiding the occurrence of danger and evil in the *PT*, see MEURER, 2002: 99 ff.

¹⁵² See e.g.: *PT*, 215: 42-43; *PT*, 222: 49-51.

¹⁵³ See TE VELDE, 1967: 27 ff.

¹⁵⁴ This incidence is often only alluded to in the *PT*, and often Seth's name is left out or replaced by epithets: see e.g.: *PT*, 477: 164-65, *PT*, 703: 306 ff; for a complete list of such instances alluding to the contendings of Osiris and Seth, see MEURER, 2002: 101 ff.

¹⁵⁵ See *Physics*, II.2: 241 ff.

¹⁵⁶ See *Nicomachian Ethics*, VII: 1036-58.

¹⁵⁷ See Section II.4, *supra*.

pursuit of wisdom, but on the contrary are driven by desires for domination and luxury, which ultimately leave them dissatisfied and full of self-hatred. Aristotle calls such specimen *evil* (κακός, φαῦλος)¹⁵⁸. This *πλεονεξία* (= the desire for more and more) appears to be the natural deficiency innate in Seth and ultimately drives him killing his brother Osiris out of jealousy and desire for dominion on Earth¹⁵⁹.

FIGURE IV: 1. [LEFT]: The holy cat of Rē^c slaughtering ˆApophis under the sacred perseae-tree, thus restoring Maˆat. Detail of a painting from the Tomb of Inherkhˆau (TT 359, Dynasty XX).
2. [RIGHT]: Similar motif with the Great Cat of Heliopolis slaughtering and deactivating the evil demon ˆApophis. Detail of a painting from the Tomb of Nakht-Amūn (TT 335, Dynasty XIX).

In terms of the four causes this process can be explained as following: The material cause of the creation of evil is Seth [FIG. I, II, III.1-2, IV.1-2], or maybe the intention of Seth as intelligible matter in his head. The formal cause is Seth’s mental deficiency which imagined the rebellion against Order and thus formed a blueprint of *isft* in his mind. This deficiency simultaneously acted as the efficient cause, represented by his jealousy and desire for domination. The *telos* or *final cause* at last is the origin of *isft* in the ordered world. Alternatively the material cause of evil can be perceived as being potentially present in the Nūn from which Seth developed as agent of the formal and efficient cause of evil¹⁶⁰.

The creation of evil brought with it the creation of the Underworld [FIG. I, III.1-2], a place that exists separately but in between the physical, ordered world and the realms of primeval chaos and potentiality, that is Nūn¹⁶¹. The process, again only alluded to in the *Pyramid Texts*, was a direct and necessary response to the fratricide committed by Seth¹⁶². Thus the *telos* of the creation of evil functioned at the same time as the efficient cause for the creation of the Netherworld which was made by Atūm as a Kingdom for the resurrected Osiris¹⁶³. The material cause can be interpreted once again as having been potentially present in the primeval waters. The formal cause originated from the mind of Atūm. Evil (death being its apex) —as was already said above— acted as an efficient cause and the final cause was the restoration of Maˆat [FIG. II, IV.1-2], which was so rudely violated¹⁶⁴.

¹⁵⁸ See n. 157, *supra*; cf. esp. *Nicoma. Eth.*, VII: 4 ff, 1042 ff.

¹⁵⁹ See n. 155, *supra*.

¹⁶⁰ See SMITH, 1994: 67-88; ASSMANN, 1994: 93-100 (for a detailed account on the origins and development of *isft*).

¹⁶¹ See HORNUNG, 1965: 73 ff.

¹⁶² See n. 154, *supra*.

¹⁶³ See e.g.: PT, 219: 46-48.

¹⁶⁴ See e.g.: ASSMANN, 1994: 174 ff; MEURER, 2002: esp. 139 ff. On the non-existence of death at the very beginning, see especially PT, 571: 226 and n. 81, *supra*.

III. ARISTOTELIAN PRIME MOVER AND ANCIENT EGYPTIAN DEMIURGE

Having divided the ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies into their four causal components it seems advisable to discuss the whole process of creation and its agent comprehensively¹⁶⁵. It cannot have escaped the attention of the reader that there exist certain differences in the nature of Aristotle's Unmoved Mover and the ancient Egyptian Demiurge, which derive from the initially introduced disparity of ancient Hellenic and ancient Egyptian philosophical thoughts. Aristotle arrives at a Prime or Unmoved Mover by means of rationally tracing the causality of things, which are more familiar to him, backwards until he reaches a point where an Unmoved Mover has to be assumed to avert contradictions¹⁶⁶. The ancient Egyptians on the other hand relied on symbolic mythology to explain the origin of natural and abstract mental phenomena. Nevertheless, the fact that they too arrive at a concept of a Self-Created Creator, if slightly different in nature, demonstrates a similar (virtually rational) way of thought¹⁶⁷.

FIGURE V: Sculpted head of the glorious Hellenic Philosopher Aristotle (384-322 BC), tutor of Alexander the Great. Copy of a lost bronze sculpture made by Lysippos, dating from the Roman Imperial Era (1st or 2nd Century AD), made of Pentelic marble. Musée du Louvre, N^o MR 329 / MA 80B.

Aristotle [FIG. V] first observed that everything in this world changes, that is it either causes changes to others, or causes changes to itself¹⁶⁸. However, this process cannot be traced back infinitely, but at one point there must be a Substance, or a Being which can move others but is itself unmoved¹⁶⁹. At the same time natural change occurs because all living beings aspire towards something higher, in an attempt to excel in their natural traits¹⁷⁰. Aristotle thus concludes that there must be a separate Being which is itself the most Perfect Substance to which all other beings strive. Being an absolutely Perfect Creature, this Substance cannot itself contain any material source, for matter is the origin of change and deficiencies. It is therefore entirely

¹⁶⁵ For the sake of brevity, the following discussion will exclusively focus on Atūm of the Heliopolitan and Hermopolitan Cosmogonies, however many points can equally be applied to Ptah of the Memphite Theology, which is based on and continues the earlier traditions. See also FINNESTAD, 1976: 85 ff; cf. TATOMIR, 2009, 503-21.

¹⁶⁶ In *Metaphysics*, IV.3: 736 ff Aristotle introduces the principle of non-contradiction as a philosophical axiom, i.e.: an unquestionable truth upon which philosophical thought can be based. See also: BARNES, 1995: 101-08.

¹⁶⁷ See e.g.: ALLEN, 1988: 48 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 58 ff.

¹⁶⁸ See Section II, *supra*.

¹⁶⁹ See *Physics*, II.3: 241; *Metaphysics*, I.2: 691 ff; V.2: 752 ff.

¹⁷⁰ See Section II.4, *supra*; cf. also *Metaphysics*, VIII.11: 800 ff.

simple actuality and pure form¹⁷¹. Consequently this Being must itself be unchanging or unmoving while it moves everything in the world around it. It is thus both, pure actuality and activity¹⁷².

According to Aristotle, the only way of estimating the nature of this obscure Being, is to take the only comparatively perfect and purely actual entity familiar to human understanding, namely the mind itself, as blueprint indicator of the Divine¹⁷³. Since the goal of the human mind is to pursue happiness and pleasure, Aristotle proposes that the activity of the Unmoved Mover equally pursues or even consists in intense pleasure. Unlike the human mind, this desire is never corrupted by the material part of a compound substance¹⁷⁴. Finally, it would be contradictory to deny life to this purely Perfect Being, for the lack of life would be a sign of deficiency¹⁷⁵. In summary, Aristotle's obscure Unmoved Mover is a simple, unchanging, entirely perfect living substance. It consists of and subsists in pure pleasure, but, as all living beings, aspires towards something. Since there is nothing more perfect than the Unmoved Mover the only thing He naturally desires is Himself¹⁷⁶. In a process that according to Aristotle escapes the imperfect human mind, the nature of the world as a whole attributes to the desire of this Supreme Being¹⁷⁷. Accordingly, Aristotle is certain that there can only be one Unmoved Mover. He argues that if there were more, they could only differ numerically as members of a species, as, for example, Socrates and Plato are distinct members of the human species. But since individualism is determined by matter, this would presuppose that the Unmoved Mover is just as much a composite being as human, which is impossible¹⁷⁸.

Although the ancient Egyptians did not leave behind any accounts of an equally rational approach to a Demiurge, they nevertheless realized that the world and beings around them must have had an ultimate beginning. In the Old and Middle Kingdom this origin was predominantly personified as the creator god Atūm, or as one of his derivative aspects¹⁷⁹. The god's name itself reflects his mysterious nature. The word *tm* can both refer to the verb «to complete» or the negatival verb, meaning «that which is not», or «not yet»¹⁸⁰. Thus, Atūm embodies the completeness of everything that not yet is, but will ultimately come into existence. The former alludes to his subsistence in the primeval ocean Nūn, the latter to the moment of *first occasion*, that is the very moment when Atūm became conscious and rose from the primeval abyssal waters on the primordial mound¹⁸¹. In this form, as the complete and null, the ancient Egyptians, too, perceived their Creator as eternal. Atūm pre-existed in the Nūn before creation and will dissolve back into it at the end of time¹⁸². As discussed in Section II.4 (*supra*), Atūm,

¹⁷¹ See *Metaphysics*, XII: 872-88, esp. XII.6: 877 ff; *Nicomachean Ethics*, VII.14: 1056-58; see also: DEFILIPPO, 1994: 400 ff.

¹⁷² See n. 170, *supra*.

¹⁷³ See e.g.: *Metaphysics*, XII.9: 884 ff.

¹⁷⁴ See *Metaphysics*, XII.6: 877 ff; *Physics*, VIII: 354-94.

¹⁷⁵ See *Metaphysics*, XII.6-8: 877-81, esp. 880.

¹⁷⁶ For if he was to aspire towards a higher, thus more perfect being, he would not be the most perfect *Unmoved Mover* anymore, which would be a contradiction and thus impossible; see *Metaphysics*, XII: esp 6 ff, 877 ff; see also DEFILIPPO, 1994: 400 ff; GOTTHELF, 1976: 226 ff.

¹⁷⁷ Aristotle never elaborates this process, which thus remains rather obscure and unconvincing. See *De Caelo*, I: 398-428; cf. also: ALLAN, 1970: 86 ff.

¹⁷⁸ See e.g.: *Metaphysics*, XII.6: 877 ff.

¹⁷⁹ So, for instance, in the form of the sun-god Rē^c: see e.g.: *PT*, 215: 42-43, *PT*, 217: 44-45; or in the form of Rē^c-Atūm-Nūn: *CT*, 75, I: 72-77. See QUIRKE, 2001: 24 ff, 73-114; HORNUNG, 2005: 89-100.

¹⁸⁰ See ALLEN, 2000: 169-70; BONNET, 2000, 71-74: art. «Atūm»; ASSMANN, 2005: 14.

¹⁸¹ See *PT*, 600: 246 ff; *PT*, 606: 250 ff. Cf. also MARAVELIA, 2006: 399-400 (for comparisons with modern Cosmology).

¹⁸² See e.g.: *PT*, 571: 226-27; *CT*, 80, I: 83-87; *BD*: 175 (as translated in DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 67).

too, can under certain circumstances be perceived as pure perfection, aspired by all other living substances. However, despite these indisputable similarities between the Aristotelian and the ancient Egyptian Prime Mover, still there also exist substantial differences.

The most obvious concerns the creational act of the physical world. In *De Cælo*, Aristotle explains that the Universe, the celestial bodies and the four substantial elements are eternal and animated by the Unmoved Mover¹⁸³. Changes and varieties on Earth are explained by: **1.** The transformation of the four elements into each other and consequently the origin of different forms and materials; and **2.** The natural aspiration of beings towards the best possible shape most suitable for their individual purpose¹⁸⁴. Everything outside this physical world has neither spatial nor temporal dimension, and it is thus not only contradictory but also plainly ludicrous to inquire in the origin or dimensions of the Unmoved Mover¹⁸⁵.

The latter idea is paralleled in the ancient Egyptian perception of Nūn. Before the *first occasion* there was neither time nor space nor life, just the chaotic primeval mass which had no dimensions¹⁸⁶. For this reason the ancient Egyptians themselves never seem to have inquired into the origin or nature of Nūn¹⁸⁷. The ancient Egyptian Demiurge pre-existed in this watery abyss potentially, in contrast to the eternal actuality of Aristotle's Unmoved Mover. The origin of the physical world occurred when Atūm (in a mysterious way) became conscious of himself¹⁸⁸. In the Hermopolitan Cosmogony the four primeval elements, *darkness* (σκοτεινότης), *hiddenness* (κρυπτότης), *formlessness* (ἀμορφία) and *watery abyss* (ὕδατῶδες χάος), lifted the creator god out of the Nūn, concealed either in an egg or a lotus flower, and thus initiated the self-realization of the Demiurge¹⁸⁹. In the Heliopolitan tradition, it was Atūm's dialogue with the primeval water that caused him to put his daughter Tefnūt/Order to his nose in order to live and apparently triggered his consciousness¹⁹⁰.

Following that self-perception, the development of the physical world began. In a process which resembles natural generation, Atūm brought about both his children Shū and Tefnūt by means of self-impregnation through masturbation, and/or the media of spitting, sneezing or exhalation¹⁹¹. However, several Scholars have correctly pointed out that this process was only a familiarized and allegoric way through which the ancient Egyptians tried to explain the abstract multiplication of the Demiurge¹⁹². This multiplication resembles cell division (*mitōsis*) rather than natural generation through conception and birth¹⁹³. Shū and Tefnūt are essentially parts of Atūm who subsist with him in the Nūn¹⁹⁴.

¹⁸³ See *De Cælo*, I.12: 423 ff; cf. also ALLAN, 1970: 92 ff.

¹⁸⁴ E.g.: the best possible adaptation of teeth in animals to their natural nutrition; see *Physics*, II.6: 246-47.

¹⁸⁵ See *De Cælo*, I.4: 403 ff.

¹⁸⁶ See *PT*, 571: 226-27.

¹⁸⁷ See DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 45 ff.

¹⁸⁸ See Section II.2, *supra*.

¹⁸⁹ See Sections I; II.1-2, *supra*.

¹⁹⁰ See Sections II.2-3, *supra*.

¹⁹¹ See Section II.1, *supra*.

¹⁹² See ALLEN, 1988: 27 ff; ASSMANN, 2005: 17 ff. It should be mentioned here, that the ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies distinguished between two types of Demiurges: **1.** A *self-developing Creator* who brings everything into being through himself (Atūm); and **2.** A *dependent Creator* who depends on an unmentioned or synchronized proto-creator (Ptah in the Memphite Theology, or Atūm in the Hermopolitan tradition). See ALLEN, 1988: 38 ff, 48 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 47-50; for the Ogdoad as proto-creators, see furthermore: HOLLIS, 1998: 61-72; TATOMIR, 2009, 503-21. On this virtual divine *mitōsis*, see also MARAVELIA, 2006: 395.

¹⁹³ See HORNUNG, 2005: 182 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 58 ff; ASSMANN, 2005: 30 ff; BONNET, 2000: 864-67.

¹⁹⁴ See Section II.3, *supra*.

The underlying reason for this is the complex nature of these two deities, which can only be briefly surveyed here. Both Shū and Tefnūt incorporate at least three abstract terms. Most prominently they represent two of the basic four elements of the physical world, that co-exist eternally alongside the Unmoved Mover in the Philosophy of Aristotle, namely Air (Shū) and Moisture (Tefnūt)¹⁹⁵. Moisture here seems to represent the physical element of water that exists on Earth as *rain* (*mww nw pt*), *dew* (*βdt*) or in the *waters of the Nile* (*mww nw Hꜥpy*) in contrast to the more remote, potential watery mass of the *Primordial Ocean* (*Nwn*)¹⁹⁶.

At the same time, Shū and Tefnūt are associated or equaled with the concepts of Life (Shū) and Order (Tefnūt)¹⁹⁷. As mentioned above it was their coming into existence that created a perfectly ordered and conscious (living) state¹⁹⁸. Simultaneously the two-fold concept of time was created¹⁹⁹. While Aristotle perceives the physical world as eternal, if eternally changing, ancient Egyptian *time* (*rk*) began with the *first occasion* (*zp tpy*). Before that the world resembled Aristotle's outer physical sphere, a domain void of both time and space²⁰⁰.

The time represented by Shū, or *Life/ꜥnh* was *Eternal Recurrence* (*nḥḥ*) which included the notion of change (*hpr* = *to become, develop, evolve*). It paralleled life in that it described the constantly changing conditions in the physical world. Tefnūt/Order, on the other hand, represented the notion of time known to the Egyptians as *Eternal Sameness* (*dt*), which described the circular, repetitive motion of the *first occasion*, the moment of perfect Order which to achieve — or maintain as closely as possible — was the ultimate *telos* of all inhabitants of Egypt, divine or mortal²⁰¹. The Egyptian verb corresponding to *dt*, and at the same time complementing and contrasting *hpr* was *wnn*, literally to exist²⁰². Since the notion of time in ancient Egypt is too complex to be sufficiently treated here this short introduction must suffice. Shū and Tefnūt, thus, personified the concepts of two physical elements, the abstract terms *Order* and *Life*, and the two-fold notion of time, and should thus be interpreted both as mental parts of Atūm, and as physical parts of the world.

As the latter, Shū and Tefnūt can be perceived as autonomous deities who are responsible for the continuity of generation. By means of both natural conception and birth Shū and Tefnūt brought about the god Geb and the goddess Nūt²⁰³. This way continuous generation could be secured. However, Geb and Nūt were madly in love from the start and would not loosen their embrace. Although Nūt had conceived already, the embrace impeded natural birth. This clever mythology aimed to explain the creation of space or void in which the nature of the physical world could evolve. Ultimately, it was their father Shū, noticeably the incorporation of the element *air*, who created a void by separating his children, placing Geb on the Earth and lifting Nūt above his head, and thus inducing the birth and evolution of the next generations²⁰⁴. It is at this point that creation in the Aristotelian sense of artistic production first took

¹⁹⁵ See BONNET, 32000, 685-89: art. «Shū»; *op. cit.*, 770-74: art. «Tefnūt»; see also Section II.1, *supra*.

¹⁹⁶ In the latter case *Moisture* should probably be perceived as existing within the productive forces of the primordial abysmal ocean Nūn, which actually constitute both the River Nile and its annual inundation; see for example BONNET, 32000, 525-528: art. «Nil»; HORNUNG, 1956: 30 ff; ALLEN, 1988: 4 ff. Cf. also BARTEL, 2003: 49-59.

¹⁹⁷ See esp. CT, 80, I: 83-87; cf. also ASSMANN, 1994: 167 ff; ALLEN, 1988: 21 ff.

¹⁹⁸ See Section II.4, *supra*.

¹⁹⁹ See ALLEN, 1988: 24 ff; ASSMANN, 1994: 169 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 64-70; esp. ASSMANN, 1975.

²⁰⁰ See n. 199, *supra*; cf. also *De Cælo*, I: 398-428.

²⁰¹ See n. 199, *supra*. On the two notions of eternity (*nḥḥ* and *dt*), see also SERVAJEAN, 2007.

²⁰² See CT, 335^{I-II}, I: 260-69; CT, 80, I: 83-87; CT, 78, I: 81-82; cf. also ALLEN, 1988: 24 ff.

²⁰³ See e.g.: CT, 75-80, I: 72-87; *pBremner-Rhind* (the *Scroll of Overthrowing ʿApep*, as translated in ALLEN, 1988: 28 ff); cf. also ASSMANN, 2005: 17 ff. On Nūt, cf. also MARAVELIA, 2003: 55-72.

²⁰⁴ See n. 203, *supra*; ALLEN, 1988: 14 ff; HORNUNG, 2005: 180 ff.

place, for separating Sky and Earth was a thoroughly considered teleological event²⁰⁵. In summary, the origin of the world took place in three steps: **1.** Self-development and self-multiplication by Atūm. **2.** Natural generation by Shū and Tefnūt. **3.** Creation of the void by Shū and continuation of natural generation by Geb and Nūt, and subsequently by Osiris and Isis²⁰⁶.

The creation of the void brought with it another important development. It provided space for the daily and nocturnal course of the Sun, the source and centre of life in the physical world²⁰⁷. Two ideas on how the Sun came into being prevail in Old and Middle Kingdom sources. The most fundamental one marks the *first occasion* as the first appearance of the Sun on the primeval mound²⁰⁸. The second describes how Shū and Tefnūt got lost in the primeval water after Atūm had generated them. The «worried father» took his «Sole Eye» in order to «give brilliance to the Darkness» and thus retrieve them²⁰⁹. Later myths continued this story more coherently. When the successful solar eye returned to its «body» it discovered that he had already replaced it. In order to appease his furious eye, the Creator put it in the favoured position at his forehead where it would protect him from now on in the form of a spitting cobra, the well-known *uræus* (*iꜣrt*)²¹⁰.

Both explanations show that the Sun either developed with Atūm at the *first occasion* or very shortly after. In the latter context god Atūm was often synchronized with the sun-god Rē^c, as Atūm-Rē^c, that is Atūm in his form as Rē^c²¹¹. Often, the first part was dropped in context and it is for this reason that apparent contradictions such as «Rē^c is the father of Rē^c» can occur²¹². The appearance of the Sun brought with it the first light, which separated the darkness of the primeval chaos from the now enlightened ordered world and made generation and creation possible! In essence the moment of self-realization can be quite literally understood as the moment of First Enlightenment²¹³. But while *Light* (*iꜣhw, wn*) dispelled chaotic *Darkness* (*kkw*), it did not destroy it. The dark, primeval mass continued to be present even in the ordered world. If Ma^cat was violated or weakened it could easily gain access back into the small realm of ordered light, not as a substantial mass, but as the nothingness it was. This was the case during obvious transformations from light to darkness, for example sunsets, storms, solar and lunar eclipses, nightmares, misfortune and illnesses; in short, everything that lacked Order and/or Light was associated with it²¹⁴.

²⁰⁵ See esp. HORNUNG, 2005: 180 ff; and in parts 182 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004.

²⁰⁶ See n. 204, *supra*; also e.g.: PT, 600: 246-47; *pBremner-Rhind* (the *Scroll of Overthrowing ʿApep*), as translated in ALLEN, 1988: 28 ff. The creation of Humankind and other creatures was a mythologically parallel process. Since it is not strictly speaking part of the actual Cosmogonies it will not be considered in this paper. For an overview of the creation of Humankind in ancient Egypt, see e.g.: ASSMANN, 2005: 18 ff; PINCH, 2003: 66 ff; HORNUNG, 2005: 155 ff.

²⁰⁷ See ALLEN, 1988: 30 ff; ASSMANN, 1995A: 174 ff; and in parts QUIRKE, 2001: 23 ff.

²⁰⁸ See e.g.: PT, 600: 246-47; CT, 335^{I-II}, I: 260-69; see also HORNUNG, 1965: 72 ff.

²⁰⁹ See e.g.: CT, 76, I: 77-80; CT, 80, I: 83-87; CT, 1000, III: 106; cf. esp. *pBremner-Rhind* (i.e.: the *Scroll of Overthrowing ʿApep*), as translated in ALLEN, 1988: 27 ff.

²¹⁰ This cobra is commonly known as *uræus* (*iꜣrt*), or the goddess Wadjyt (*Wꜣdyt*), but later deities (most noticeably: Hathor, Sekhmet, Bastet and even Tefnūt) could also be identified with her; see BONNET, 32000, 733-35: art. «Sonnenaug»; PINCH, 2003: 128 ff.

²¹¹ See current Section III; cf. also n. 180, *supra*.

²¹² See e.g.: HORNUNG, 2005: 89 ff.

²¹³ See CT, 75-80, I: 72-87; CT, 366, II: 7; cf. ALLEN, 1988: 30-35; HORNUNG, 1965: esp. 77 ff; ASSMANN, 1995A: 174 ff.

²¹⁴ With the exception of the primordial elements Kek (*Kk*) and Heh (*Hh*), this negative chaotic darkness was never actually personified as a deity. However from at least the First Intermediate Period onwards it was represented in form of the serpent-demon and ultimate enemy of the sun-god: ʿApep. The daily battle between Rē^c and ʿApep [FIG. I, II] can thus be directly interpreted as the battle for dominion of the Light over Darkness, Order over Chaos. See e.g.: HORNUNG, 2005: 175-180; HORNUNG, 1965: 78 ff; COHN, 1993: 3-30; & c.

Despite this negative connotation of the primeval chaos, there existed a second, positive one. The primeval waters were not only the source of disorder but also the origin of all creation²¹⁵. In this context it was considered the medium of revival, rebirth and resurrection²¹⁶. It was by means of the Nūn that the sun-god, who grew old and weary during his daily course, could recover overnight and be reborn in the morning²¹⁷. It was the resurrecting ability of Nūn that aided Isis's magic in reviving Osiris²¹⁸. In the physical world Nūn was present in the fertile waters of the Nile which were believed to originate directly from the primeval ocean itself²¹⁹.

EXCURSUS II: ARISTOTELIAN ACTUALITY AND POTENTIALITY AND THE NATURE OF NŪN: Considering the fundamental part the primeval ocean Nūn played in ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies it deserves to be surveyed more closely. By taking Aristotle's *Metaphysics* as our frame of reference and based on references of Nūn in the primary sources the current Excursus will strive to discuss whether the primeval ocean Nūn is Actuality or Potentiality. As initially mentioned Aristotle perceives all definable substances as hylomorphic compounds of matter and form²²⁰. Matter according to him is *mere potentiality* (δύναμις), i.e.: a changeable, formable mass that is only made actual by combining it with the *actual* form, the universal image that pre-exists in the mind. These ideas or forms are in contrast to matter and constitute mere actuality (ἐντελέχεια or ἐνέργεια)²²¹.

Δύναμις or *Potentiality* is perceived in two different senses. On the one hand it is the «source of change in something else», that is the potential a thing possesses to move and to produce a change (κίνησις). On the other hand δύναμις is the capacity of a thing to become something different and more complete²²². Taken as such potentiality is indefinable when separated from some actuality. To clarify the terms, Aristotle states that actuality is to potentiality like «the walking [is] to the sleeping»²²³. Perhaps then it could be that δύναμις + κίνησις ≈ *sh̄m/b̄šw*.

In terms of creation, both as artistic production and natural generation, Aristotle places actuality prior to potentiality, both temporal and causal²²⁴. As stated in Section II.4 and the current Section III (see *supra*) Aristotle argues rationally that the Unmoved Mover must by all means be pure actuality to avoid contradictions and infinite regress. Similarly the cause of any *telos* must be *actual*. It is true that an actual oak-tree evolves from the potential acorn. An artist can only materialize the idea of a bronze sphere and thus make it into a definable substance by means of the matter bronze. But the acorn would not exist at all without previously having been produced by an oak-tree, and without the actual idea of a bronze sphere, bronze matter would eternally remain just that²²⁵. It is therefore actuality that necessarily has to exist in order to form and turn potentiality *actual*.

²¹⁵ See BONNET, ³2000: 535-36; COHN, 1993: 5 ff; HORNUNG, 1965: 81 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 45 ff, 53 ff.

²¹⁶ See n. 215, *supra*.

²¹⁷ See Section III; ASSMANN, 1995A: 174-99; HORNUNG, 2005: 159 ff.

²¹⁸ See e.g.: *PT*, **219**: 46-47; *PT*, **482**: 169 ff; *PT*, **532**: 199-200; and in parts *PT*, **576**: 231-32; see esp. MEURER, 2002: 100 ff, 167 ff; PINCH, 2003: 149 ff, 178 ff; BONNET, ³2000: 326 ff, 568 ff.

²¹⁹ See n. 197, *supra*. For a schematic comparison between ancient Egyptian and ancient Hellenic (Orphic) cosmological notions, see MARAVELIA, 2006: 365-74; MARAVELIA, 2007: 1243-50 & fig. 1.

²²⁰ See Section I, *supra*.

²²¹ See esp. *Metaphysics*, **V.12**: 765-67; **IX.2**: 821 ff.

²²² See *Metaphysics*, **IX.5-8**: 824-28.

²²³ See *Metaphysics*, **IX.6**: 826.

²²⁴ See *Metaphysics*, **IX.8**: 828 ff.

²²⁵ See n. 224, *supra*.

Returning to the subject matter of this paper, the question remains whether the primeval water Nūn takes on the role of actuality or potentiality? From the previous discussion it seems obvious that Nūn is mere potentiality, the equivalent to Aristotle's frequently hinted to but never outspoken «Prime Matter»²²⁶. If this is true Nūn would be the Prime Matter, the mere potentiality that exists eternally, waiting to be formed and actualized by an equally eternal actual substance, or at least by a compound substance, as these last two contain a clearly dominating actual part²²⁷.

The ancient texts seem to support this nature of Nūn as a matter which pre-existed virtually everything else²²⁸. But Nūn is at the same time the origin of the self-developing Demiurge, who subsisted in the water in a state of inertia and is sometimes even identified with Nūn²²⁹. According to Aristotle, however, nothing actual can develop from mere potentiality without an actual agent²³⁰. Considering Nūn as mere potentiality would thus contradict with the actuality of the Demiurge who as a self-developing, original substance, cannot be mere potentiality either. Considering then that the Creator was originally part of the Nūn, it seems to follow that Nūn and not the Demiurge must be mere actuality. Consequently, Atūm would not be the first, but the second *actual* step in the development of the world. It appears then that Nūn is the original eternal actuality which desires itself, and for this reason developed Atūm and initiated the subsequent processes²³¹. In support of this theory is certainly the productive nature of Nūn, as already previously stated (see the current Section III, *supra*).

However this assumption contradicts with the destructive, chaotic force of nothingness in the primeval waters, and which as a deficiency can only be potential²³². In addition, if Nūn was eternal actuality and thus a merely formal being, where would the first physical matter come from, which constituted millions and millions of subsequent compound substances? The ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies did not have an equivalent to Aristotle's four physical elements. The problem of the true nature of Nūn seems thus to be insolvable and to remain as obscure and mysterious as already the ancient Egyptians perceived it to be²³³.

But this is not the case. In fact the issue can be solved fairly easily if one refrains from Aristotle's priority of actuality for the origin of everything else. What many modern philosophers ignore is the fact that the Prime Mover in Aristotle does not persist alone for eternity. He merely exists separately from the physical world²³⁴. The eternal celestial bodies and four elements constitute an eternal, potential counterpart to the eternal actuality of the Unmoved Mover²³⁵. But while these two eternities are separated in Aristotle, they occur united as Nūn in the ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies. Considering Nūn not as eternal prime matter or eternal actuality, but rather as an eternal hylomorphic compound, accounts for both the material origin of things and the presence of mere actuality in form of the creator god in its midst. The *first occasion* is in fact a catalyst that dissolves this unity for the sake of development²³⁶! Much

²²⁶ See Section II.1, *supra*.

²²⁷ See BARNES, 1995: 94 ff, 127 ff.

²²⁸ See Section II.1, *supra*.

²²⁹ See Section II.1, *supra*.

²³⁰ See n. 225, *supra*; cf. also: *Metaphysics*, V.11: 763-65.

²³¹ See e.g.: DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 45-47; PINCH, 2003: 172 ff; esp. HORNUNG, 2005: 182 ff.

²³² See e.g.: Section II.5.

²³³ See DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 49.

²³⁴ See current Section III; cf. also *De Cælo*, I: 398-428.

²³⁵ See DEFILIPPO, 1994: 392 ff.

²³⁶ See e.g.: ALLEN, 1988: 14 ff; DUNAND & ZIVIE-COCHE, 2004: 47 ff, 50 ff; compare also to this Section III, *supra*.

like Geb and Nūt later had to be separated, Nūn and Atūm, incorporated in the synchronized deity Atūm–Nūn, had to be split in order to spark generation and development, and trade eternal inertia for active actuality²³⁷. This process of separation, which is often less obvious in the Heliopolitan Cosmogony, has been personified by the Hermopolitan Ogdoad²³⁸. Similarly in the Memphite Theology the unity of Ptah–Nūn (Ptah–Nūnet), who directly corresponds to Nūn–Atūm of the Heliopolitan and Hermopolitan tradition, had to be separated and arise as Ptah–Tathenen in order for creation to begin²³⁹.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The previous study has been long and intense. Comparing two such fundamentally different world views naturally leads to contradictions and perhaps dead ends, but it can also lead to a rather fruitful outcome. In a pursuit of eliminating the common assumption that the ancient Egyptians in contrast to the ancient Hellēnes had not understood the concept of rational abstraction, the present author compared three substantial parts of Aristotle’s *Metaphysics*, namely Causality, the rational concept of an Unmoved Mover and the concepts of Actuality and Potentiality to the ancient Egyptian Cosmogonies of Heliopolis, Hermopolis and Memphis. The following conclusions can be drawn: **1.** All the three Cosmogonies possess an underlying causality which closely resembles Aristotle’s Four Causes. **2.** While the views concerning the First Creator differ, both cultures derive at an unchanging origin of the physical world. In Aristotle, this Unmoved Mover exists as eternal actuality separately from the eternal elements of the physical Universe, namely the celestial bodies and the four elements, air, water, fire and earth, which ultimately constitute all other compound substances of the Cosmos. In ancient Egypt this Prime Mover is innate in the primeval water, Nūn, which hints to an allegoric unity of the eternal actual and potential parts that are separated in Aristotle’s Universe [FIG. VI]. By means of a miraculous self–realization, this unity was divided by the creator god Atūm (aided by the Ogdoad in the Hermopolitan tradition) so that evolution could take place. **3.** Accordingly, the ancient Egyptians were very much aware of the Aristotelian concepts of Actuality and Potentiality, even though these abstract concepts were personified or metaphorically united in substantial deities. On a first glance this might cause contradictions within the coherency of a given text, but these can be easily resolved once the superficial symbolism of allegories is disclosed.

The outcome clearly indicates a rational understanding of causality and abstraction, if on a less elaborated scale than in ancient Hellas. The reason for philosophical stagnancy in ancient Egypt is rooted in the world concept of Ma’at, which did not eliminate the development of new ideas, but indisputably restricted them, through the atavism characterizing the ancient Egyptian mind and habits. Since the scope of this paper allowed only for a small inquiry into the topic of ancient Egyptian Philosophy, confined to arbitrarily chosen samples, much more research towards this direction needs to be done, in order to provide a broader picture!

²³⁷ See e.g.: *CT*, 75, I: 72-77; cf. also HORNUNG, 2005: 180 ff, 182 ff.

²³⁸ See Section II.3, *supra*.

²³⁹ See ALLEN, 1988: 27 ff, 38 ff; see Section II.1, *supra*. This initial unity and separation of primeval potentiality and actuality continues in the physical world, for example in the actual form of the sun–god Rē^c in all his variations, and his potential counterpart, i.e.: Osiris. They too comprise a circular unity which is separated by the physical world at day and which is united at night–time in the Nūn. When both dissolve back into the Nūn at the end of time, the hylomorphic unity will once again exist undisturbed, until another, mysterious incidence causes its separation, in order to trigger a new generation. See e.g.: HORNUNG, 1999; MARAVELIA, 2006: 397 & n. 114.

It is important to remain aware, however, that such a study is always undertaken by a modern mind reflecting on two ancient high cultures from a modern —rather biased— point of view and reference. Due to these obvious restrictions, in addition to the rather fragmentary sources available, modern Scholars can of course never be absolutely certain about the nature and quintessence of either ancient Philosophy.

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